

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ҲУҚУҚНИ МУҲОФАЗА ҚИЛИШ
АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

**“Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш фаолияти соҳасида
глобал чақириқлар ва таҳдидлар:
муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзусидаги халқаро
конференция материаллари
Т Ў П Л А М И
I-жилд**

**“Глобальные вызовы и угрозы в сфере
правоохранительной деятельности:
проблемы и решения” материалы
международной конференции
СБОРНИК
Том I**

**"Global challenges and threats in law
enforcement: problems and solutions"
materials of the international conference
COLLECTION
VOLUME I**

ТОШКЕНТ – 2025

ЎУК: 343.195.3:343.163(575.1)
КБК: 67.7+67.4
Ҳ 97

Мазкур тўплам Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси Кенгашининг 2025 йил 15 февралдаги 1-сонли қарори билан нашрга тавсия қилинган.

“Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш фаолияти соҳасидаги глобал чақириқлар ва таҳдидлар: муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзусида халқаро конференция материаллари тўплами. I-жилд // Масъул муҳаррир ю.ф.д., проф. М.М.Мамасиддиқов, ю.ф.ф.д., доц. Ш.И.Шайзаков. – Т.: Lesson press. 2025.–541 б.

Масъул муҳаррир: ю.ф.д., проф. **М.М.Мамасиддиқов**
ю.ф.ф.д., доц. **Ш.И.Шайзаков**

Таҳрир ҳайъати: ю.ф.д., проф. **Б.Х.Пўлатов**
ю.ф.д., проф. **Ф.Х.Рахимов**
ю.ф.д., проф. **В.Каримов**
ю.ф.д., проф. **М.А.Аминжонова**

Нашрга тайёрловчилар: ю.ф.ф.д., доцент **Ш.И.Шайзаков**
таянч докторант **Ш.А.Мажидов**

Тўпламда Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси ташкил этилганлигининг икки йиллиги муносабати билан бўлиб ўтган “Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш фаолияти соҳасидаги глобал чақириқлар ва таҳдидлар: муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзусида халқаро конференция материаллари ўрин олган. Унда ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш соҳасидаги таҳдидлар, жумладан коррупция, жиноий маблағларни қонунийлаштириш, терроризмни молиялаштиришга қарши курашишда янги чақириқ ва тенденциялар, тергов фаолиятида рақамли криминалистиканинг аҳамияти, ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш соҳасида фан ва таълим, сунъий интеллектни қўллаш, одам савдоси билан боғлиқ жиноятларни тергов қилиш устидан прокурор назорати самарадорлигини ошириш масалалари юзасидан илмий ва амалий тажриба, фикрлар алмашинувини ўз ичига олади.

Тўплам фан ва таълим соҳасини бошқаришга ваколатли давлат органлари, юридик фан ва ҳуқуқни қўллаш амалиёти билан боғлиқ хорижий давлатларнинг етук олимлари, мутасадди ташкилотлар ходимлари, Ўзбекистон Республикасининг юридик фанлар соҳасида кўзга кўринган етук олимлари, профессор-ўқитувчилар, мустақил изланувчилар, докторантлар, магистрлар бошқа ёш олимларнинг мақола ва тезислари баён этилган.

Мазкур тўпламга киритилган материалларнинг мазмуни, ундаги статистик ва бошқа маълумотлар, меъёрий ҳужжатлар санасининг тўғрилигига ҳамда танқидий фикр-мулоҳазаларга муаллифларнинг шахсан ўзлари масъулдирлар.

© Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси, 2025.

collected as a reward¹. The creation of the legal basis for the notification system in the United States in 1778 was caused by two commanding officers named Richard Marven and Samuel Shaw². In particular, Richard Marven and Samuel Shaw witnessed how their kumondo, Esek Hopkins, tortured British prisoners of war. As a result, they decided to report the incident committed by their leaders, as the committed behavior was contrary to the law. However, there was no legal protection for crime-reporting individuals in the United States at the time. As a result, on July 30, 1778, the Continental Congress passed the Whistleblower Protection Act³.

We believe that historically, the United States has developed an "information" mechanism as an effective measure to ensure the safe and effective functioning of the government, combat corruption crimes, and create a legal framework. In particular, in the United States, the main legislation regarding informants has been developed by States, which, in accordance with this statute, establish that citizens can report crimes they report, as well as inform federal employees about violations by the employer of certain laws, rules or regulations.

In conclusion, it is appropriate to note that although the form of government in most States today is historically fundamentally different from monarchical rule, there is still a need for a notification mechanism for the prevention and disclosure of crimes committed at that time. This, in turn, led to the creation of the legal framework for the notification system in the national legislation of many States.

SHAYZAKOV SHODIYOR IBRAGIMOVICH
Head of the Center at the Law Enforcement
Academy, PhD in Law, associate professor,
independent researcher

CONSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE REVIEW OF CIVIL COURT DECISIONS IN THE CASSATION INSTANCE

Annotation: *The institution of cassation review of civil court decisions is an essential guarantee of justice, legality, and the protection of citizens' rights in society. This article analyzes the constitutional and legal foundations of the cassation institution in Uzbekistan, along with its theoretical and practical aspects. In particular, it proposes improving legislation, enhancing judicial qualifications, and introducing electronic document circulation and automated systems to refine the judicial review process. The cassation procedure serves as a*

¹ New York City During the American Revolution. Internet Archive: Mercantile Library Association. 1861. p. 11 et seq.

² Grassley, Charles (August 1, 2013). "Honoring America's Truth Tellers". Grassley.Senate.Gov. US Government. Retrieved August 2, 2014.

³ Washington, Government Printing Office (1708). "Journals of the Continental Congress: 1794 - 1799, pp. 732-33".

crucial mechanism for ensuring the fairness of judicial decisions, eliminating judicial errors, and strengthening the rule of law.

Keywords: *Constitution, Cassation, Civil Court Decisions, Legality, Judicial System, Legislative Improvement, Judges, Electronic Document Circulation, Automated Systems.*

Аннотация: *Фуқаролик суд ҳужжатларини кассация инстанциясида қайта кўриш институти жамиятда адолат, қонунийлик ва фуқароларнинг ҳуқуқларини ҳимоя қилишнинг муҳим кафолати ҳисобланади. Ушбу мақолада кассация институтининг Ўзбекистондаги конституциявий ва ҳуқуқий асослари, унинг назарий ва амалий жиҳатлари таҳлил қилинади. Хусусан, суд ҳужжатларини қайта кўриш тизимини такомиллаштириш учун қонунчиликни яхшилаш, судьялар малакасини ошириш ва электрон ҳужжат айланмаси ҳамда автоматлаштирилган тизимларни жорий этиш таклиф қилинади. Кассация жараёни суд қарорларининг адолатлилигини таъминлашда, суд хатоларини бартараф этишда ва ҳуқуқий устуворликни мустаҳкамлашда муҳим механизм бўлиб хизмат қилади.*

Калит сўзлар: *Конституция, Кассация, фуқаролик суд ҳужжатлари, қонунийлик, суд тизими, қонунчиликни такомиллаштириш, судьялар, электрон ҳужжат айланмаси, автоматлаштирилган тизимлар.*

The review and resolution of civil court decisions play a crucial role in ensuring fair justice within society. Issuing just decisions in this sphere and safeguarding the legal interests of every individual are among the fundamental principles of constitutional law. The institution of reviewing civil court decisions in the cassation instance serves as an essential legal mechanism that guarantees the protection of citizens' rights and safeguards their interests.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees the independence of the judiciary, emphasizing the principles of justice and legality in judicial proceedings. Moreover, the right to review decisions made in civil cases enhances fairness and trust in the judicial process. This institution is aimed at ensuring legality in society, correcting errors and deficiencies in court decisions, and fully protecting the rights of individuals involved in legal proceedings.

The institution of reviewing cases in the cassation instance is an integral part of legal justice, contributing to the development of judicial and legal reforms. Through the review process, citizens and other interested parties gain greater confidence in the fairness of court decisions, thereby strengthening trust in the establishment of a legal state.

The institution of reviewing civil cases in the cassation instance has emerged and developed not only as an integral part of Uzbekistan's legal system but also as a fundamental component of the legislation in many countries worldwide. The cassation instance serves to reassess the fairness and legality of judicial decisions and has been established to ensure the full protection of citizens' rights.

From a historical development perspective, the cassation institution has existed since ancient times, with its roots tracing back to Roman law. In Roman law, great attention was given to ensuring the fairness and legality of court

decisions. In modern legal systems, the significance of the cassation process has further increased, and its scope has expanded. The cassation institution remains one of the most crucial mechanisms for ensuring justice and legality within legal systems.

According to legal scholar A. Abdullin, the cassation process plays a crucial role in the review of judicial decisions, as it contributes to the development of the judicial system and ensures legality. He emphasizes that the cassation institution helps strengthen citizens' trust in the judicial system.¹

Additionally, Y. Tikhomirov emphasizes that the institution of review in the cassation instance provides an opportunity to make legally fair decisions, making it a crucial tool for protecting the legal interests of citizens. The review of judicial decisions is one of the fundamental conditions for restoring justice and ensuring legality.²

Furthermore, in developed countries such as France, Germany, and England, the cassation institution has evolved over centuries, becoming a crucial part of ensuring justice within the judicial system. In particular, in France, the Court of Cassation is the highest court in the general judicial system, responsible for reviewing civil court decisions and striving to uphold legality.

Regarding the theoretical foundations of the institution of civil case review, its primary objective is to ensure the legality and fairness of judicial decisions. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the review of civil cases is a constitutional guarantee of the right to appeal to the courts, with its main function being the protection of citizens' rights and freedoms.

When discussing the significance of the cassation process in ensuring fairness, it is important to highlight that the review of civil cases allows for the correction of judicial errors, thereby creating a legal safeguard for justice within the judicial system. This institution serves as a vital legal mechanism for individuals seeking protection in civil matters.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the supremacy of the law, justice, and guarantees of legal protection, all of which play a crucial role in safeguarding citizens' interests. In this process, the independence of the judiciary is also of great importance, as an independent judicial system ensures guaranteed opportunities for the protection of citizens' rights.

According to the constitutional provisions on the judiciary, every individual has the right to legal protection through the courts. Article 55 of the Constitution of Uzbekistan emphasizes the importance of the institution of judicial review to enhance trust in the fairness and legality of court decisions. This article also includes legal guarantees aimed at ensuring the professional independence of judges during the review process.

¹ Абдуллин А.И. Судебный прецедент в системе источников права Европейского Союза // Правовая политика и правовая жизнь. 2012. № 2. С. 144-149.

² Монография «Юридический конфликт»: монография / О.А. Акопян, С.Б. Бальхаева, А.А. Головина [и др.]; отв. ред. Ю.А. Тихомиров. – М. : ИНФРА-М: Институт законодательства и сравнительного правоведения при Правительстве РФ, 2017. – 312 с.

Additionally, to uphold the rule of law, the institution of reviewing civil cases in the cassation instance is widely applied in developed democratic countries. For example, in the United States, the Supreme Court serves as the primary legal authority for protecting citizens' rights and freedoms. In accordance with the U.S. Constitution, every individual has the right to legal protection through a fair trial, and this right is ensured through the process of judicial review.¹

In Germany, the cassation institution is built upon strong constitutional and legal foundations aimed at protecting human rights and fundamental freedoms. According to the German Constitution, safeguarding citizens' interests and correcting judicial errors are among the primary objectives of the cassation process. Through this process, German courts make a significant contribution to upholding the rule of law and ensuring justice.²

A comparative analysis of procedural legislation and its constitutional foundations in different countries demonstrates that each nation has constitutional legal grounds for the institution of judicial review, aimed at ensuring fair justice. From this perspective, it can be noted that Uzbekistan has also developed the legal foundations of this institution in accordance with international standards.

However, it is important to highlight that the process of reviewing civil court decisions in the cassation instance faces several pressing issues. These issues primarily include bureaucratic obstacles within the judicial system, deficiencies in legal provisions, the excessive workload of judges, and errors or shortcomings in decision-making.

One of the main challenges in the cassation review process is bureaucratic barriers. Although the necessary legal mechanisms exist for the functioning of the judicial system, the complexity of legal and regulatory documents significantly complicates the review process. This often leads to delays in case reconsideration, which negatively affects the principle of fair justice.

In our view, bureaucratic obstacles in the cassation process impact the efficiency of the judicial system. Therefore, improving legal mechanisms can enhance the quality of judicial review and contribute to a more effective administration of justice.

A high workload among judges reviewing cases in the cassation instance can negatively impact the quality of judicial decisions. The issue of evenly distributing caseloads among judges is a pressing concern in many countries. Excessive workloads can affect judges' concentration and attentiveness in decision-making, increasing the likelihood of errors.

To optimize the workload of judges and improve the quality of decisions in the judicial review process, additional resources need to be allocated.

¹ <https://constitution.congress.gov/browse/>

² <https://www.bmi.bund.de/EN/topics/constitution/constitutional-issues/constitutional-issues.html#:~:text=The%20current%20version%20of%20the,the%20Federal%20Republic%20of%20Germany.&text=T he%20Basic%20Law%20was%20adopted,the%20state%20until%20German%20reunification.>

Enhancing the efficiency of the cassation instance may involve appointing additional judges, engaging specialized experts in cassation courts, and incorporating artificial intelligence technologies into the judicial review process.

Improving legislation will also contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of the cassation process. While the current legal framework provides a certain level of efficiency in regulating cassation procedures, there are still some shortcomings. Specifically, the timeframes for reviewing judicial decisions, the procedures for handling cassation appeals, and the application of laws in judicial proceedings require further refinement.

To improve the process of reviewing civil court decisions in the cassation instance, a series of measures should be implemented, including legal reforms, procedural adjustments, and technological advancements.

Improving the legislative framework is crucial for enhancing the efficiency of the cassation process. By amending legislation, the judicial review process can be systematically regulated, particularly concerning deadlines for cassation appeals, the procedures for filing complaints, and the process of presenting evidence in court.

Adopting best practices from foreign countries in developing cassation instances can significantly enhance the quality of judicial reviews. For instance, cassation courts in France operate with high efficiency, making decisions based on scientific analysis and legal reasoning for each judicial document.

Certain legal sources suggest that the structured procedures and comprehensive oversight mechanisms of cassation processes in France and Germany can serve as exemplary models for other countries.

Additionally, improving the qualifications of judges is a key factor in ensuring the effectiveness of the cassation process. Enhancing professional training, optimizing the workload of judges, and organizing specialized courses on complex legal matters can contribute to a more effective cassation review process. Well-trained and highly competent judges will be better equipped to make high-quality decisions in judicial review cases.

Moreover, further development of electronic document circulation and automated systems is essential to making the judicial review process faster and more efficient. By implementing advanced digital solutions, citizens should have the ability to track the progress of their cassation appeals online without the need to physically participate in court proceedings, ensuring greater transparency and accessibility in the legal process.

The institution of cassation review for civil court decisions is one of the fundamental guarantees of justice, legality, and the protection of citizens' rights in society. Ensuring fair judicial decisions and providing an opportunity for impartial case review enhances public trust in the judiciary. The cassation process serves as a crucial mechanism for upholding the rule of law and

correcting judicial errors, thereby expanding pathways to achieving legal justice.

This article examined the constitutional and legal foundations of the cassation institution in Uzbekistan, as well as some of its theoretical and practical aspects.

In our opinion, to further develop and improve the system of reviewing civil court decisions, the following measures should be implemented:

- Simplifying the cassation process through legislative improvements;
- Enhancing the qualifications of judges and ensuring a balanced distribution of cassation workloads;
- Advancing electronic document circulation and automated systems to improve efficiency and accessibility.

In our opinion, the cassation instance, as an institution for reviewing judicial decisions in civil proceedings, possesses the following distinctive features as an independent institution:

✚ A cassation appeal (or protest) against a final decision or ruling of the first-instance court that has entered into legal force may be filed by an interested party with a higher court in accordance with the procedure established by law.

✚ Individuals participating in the case or whose rights and obligations have been determined by the court may base their cassation appeal (or protest) on violations specified in Article 3721 of the Civil Procedure Code (CPC) of the first-instance court.

✚ The cassation appeal (or protest) must be submitted to the competent court within the legally established timeframe from the date of the announcement of the final judicial decision of the first-instance court.

✚ The cassation court reviews the case, considering new arguments and additional materials, even if they were not mentioned in the appeal (or protest).

✚ Cases on cassation appeals or protests are reviewed collegially.

✚ The cassation instance has the authority to:

✚ Uphold the final decision, ruling, or judgment without changes;

✚ Fully or partially annul judicial acts and adopt a new final decision, ruling, or judgment;

✚ Amend the final decision, ruling, or judgment, either fully or partially;

✚ Dismiss the appeal based on the grounds specified in the CPC;

✚ Fully or partially terminate proceedings if procedural rules of jurisdiction were violated in the case;

✚ Annul the final decision, ruling, or judgment and transfer the case to another court based on jurisdictional rules.

In conclusion, the cassation process is a critical stage in ensuring justice and fairness in civil cases. Judicial reforms, the introduction of modern technologies, and the improvement of legal foundations will contribute to making the judicial system more efficient and transparent. The continued

development of the cassation institution is a vital step toward building a society based on the rule of law. This not only strengthens public confidence in the judiciary but also plays a significant role in fostering fairness and advancing the legal system within society.

**МАМАСИДДИҚОВ МУЗАФФАРЖОН
МУСАЖОНОВИЧ**

Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси
бошлиғининг ўринбосари, ю.ф.д., профессор

БОБОЕВ МИРШОД МУРАТОВИЧ

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Бош прокуратураси
Ахборот-коммуникация технологияларини
жорий этиш ва ахборот хавфсизлиги
бошқармаси бошлиғи, PhD

**СУД-ҲУҚУҚ СОҲАСИДА СУНЪИЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ:
ИМКОНИЯТЛАР, ХАВФ-ХАТАРЛАР ВА КАФОЛАТЛАР (ТЕЗИС)**

Сунъий интеллект тизими – бу инсон фикрлаш жараёнини компьютерда тақлид қиладиган дастурий тизимдир. У катта ҳажмдаги маълумотларни қайта ишлаш ва маълум алгоритмлар асосида қарорлар таклиф қилиш қобилиятини англатади.

Сунъий интеллект тушунчасини биринчи бўлиб **1956 йилда** америкалик информатик **Жон Маккарти** таклиф қилган. Шу йилнинг ёзида Дартмут (Dartmouth) коллежида сунъий интеллект бўйича икки ойлик илмий семинар ўтказилиши тарихий аҳамият касб этди. Мазкур семинарни молиялаштириш **Рокфеллер жамғармаси** (Rockefeller Foundation) томонидан таъминланган эди. Семинарда янги фан соҳасининг асосий қоидалари тасдиқланиб, унга илк бор инглиз тилида **“Artificial Intelligence”** – “сунъий интеллект” деган ном берилди.

Шундан буён сунъий интеллект уч маротаба ривожланиш босқичини бошдан кечирди. Бугунги кунда эса хусусан генератив сунъий интеллект инсоният ҳаётида электр энергияси, ядро технологиялари ва космосни ўзлаштириш билан тенг даражадаги ихтиро сифатида эътироф этилмоқда.

Дунё мамлакатлари халқларининг ҳаётига сунъий интеллект шиддат билан кириб келмоқда. Масалан, 2024 йилда Европа Иттифоқидаги корхоналарнинг 13,48 фоизи (йирик корхоналарнинг 41,17 фоизи) сунъий интеллект технологияларидан фойдаланган. 2023 йил билан солиштирилганда, 2024 йилда бу кўрсаткич 5,45 фоизга ошган.

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI
OLIV TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR
VAZIRLIGI HUZURIDAGI
OLIV ATTESTATSIYA
KOMISSIYASI

100047, Toshkent sh., Y. G'ulomov ko'chasi, 70
Tel.: (71) 233-28-83. Fax: (71) 233-06-47
e-mail: info@oak.uz https://oak.uz

SUPREME ATTESTATION
COMMISSION
AT THE MINISTRY OF HIGHER
EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATION
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

70, Y. Gulomov str., Tashkent, 100047
Tel.: (71) 233-28-83. Fax: (71) 233-06-47
e-mail: info@oak.uz https://oak.uz

Javob qaytarganda shu № ko'rsatibin
When you answer show this №

№ 10/3381/23 н 31 н 10 2024 у.

**Ўзбекистон Республикаси Хуқуқни муҳофаза
қилиш академиясига**

Олий аттестация комиссияси Ўзбекистон Республикаси Хуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академиясининг (22.10.2024 й., №30/5-153905/24) мурожаатига кўра Ўзбекистон Республикаси Хуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси ташкил этилганлигининг икки йиллиги муносабати билан 2024 йил 21-22 ноябрь кунлари ўтказиладиган **“Хуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш фаолияти соҳасида глобал чақириқлар ва таҳдидлар: муаммо ва ечимлар”** мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференция илмий тўпламида чоп этилган хорижий тиллардаги мақолалар диссертациялар асосий илмий натижаларини чоп этиш тавсия этилган илмий нашрлар рўйхатига киритилган хорижий илмий нашрларда чоп этилган илмий мақолаларга тенглаштирилганлигини маълум қилади.

Асос: ОАК юридик фанлар бўлимида эксперт кенгашининг тавсияси (25.10.2024 й., №10); ОАК Тартиб-қонда комиссияси қарори (30.10.2024 й., №10/24); ОАК Раёсати қарори (31.10.2024 й., №363/6).

Бош илмий котиб

А.Шермухамедов

№берчи: Т.Ш.Мангитмухамедов

Ибрагимов М.Ж. Коррупцияга оид жиноятларнинг сабаблари ва уларнинг олдини олиш	400-407
Voboxonov A.A. Issues of improving the institute of suspending preliminary investigation.....	408-412
Mirakhmedov J.M. Prevention of crimes related to robbery: comparision legal-analysis.....	412-417
Ҳолиқулова Ҳ.Ю. Лидер аёлларни тайёрлашнинг Марказий Осиё худудидаги тарихий тараққиёт босқичлари.....	418-424
Turobov V.T. Combating domestic violence as one of the urgent issues.....	424-428
Таштемиров А.А. Киберфирибгарликни фoш этишда тезкор ходим ва терговчи ўртасидаги ҳамкорликнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари.....	428-434
Хидиров Ф.Ш, Убайдуллаев Ш.М. Экстремизм ва терроризмга қарши курашининг Ўзбекистон тажрибаси.....	434-440
Ишанходжаев С.А. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг миграция соҳасидаги миллий механизмларни такомиллаштириш зарурати.....	440-454
Есемуратов А.И. Мигрантлар ҳуқуқларини ҳимоя қилишга оид халқаро-ҳуқуқий стандартлар хусусиятлари.....	454-460
Убайдуллаев Ш.М. Коррупцияга қарши курашиш Янги Ўзбекистонда давлат сиёсати.....	460-467
Қаландаров И.М. Деятельность подразделения финансовой разведки Республики Казахстан: современное состояние и перспективы развития.....	467-473
Ботаев М.Дж. Терговга қадар текширув босқичини соддалаштириш аҳамияти.....	473-477
Каримов И.И. Диний экстремизм тушунчасининг ҳуқуқий таҳлили ва унга доир замонавий илмий ёндашувлар.....	477-486
Akhmedov D.B. Institute of jurisdiction in administrative courts: comparative-legal analysis.....	486-492
Borsieva Z.Kh, Zoirova I.F. Essence of reforms to ensure children's rights to justice in the Republic of Uzbekistan.....	492-496
Majidov SH.A. Historical analysis of the emergence of the institution of reporting offenses.....	497-500
Shayzakov Sh.I. Constitutional foundations of the review of civil court decisions in the cassation instance.....	500-506
Мамасиддиқов М.М., Бобоев М.М. Суд-ҳуқуқ соҳасида сунъий интеллектдан фойдаланиш: имкониятлар, хавф-хатарлар ва кафолатлар (тезис).....	506-511
Marupov O. Features of enforcing court decisions in land-related cases.....	512-518
Шарипов З.У. Давлат ташкилотлари тасарруфидаги қишлоқ хўжалиги тўғрисидаги қонун ҳужжатлари ижроси устидан прокурор назоратини ташкил этишда хорижий давлатлар тажрибаси.....	519-530

**«ХУҚУҚНИ МУҲОҒАЗА ҚИЛИШ ФАОЛИЯТИ СОҲАСИДАГИ
ГЛОБАЛ ЧАҚИРИҚЛАР ВА ТАҲДИДЛАР:
МУАММО ВА ЕЧИМЛАР»**
мавзусидаги халқаро конференция материаллари
ТЎПЛАМИ

Техник муҳаррир:

Дизайнер:

Босишга рухсат этилди: 17.02.2025 й.

Бичими 60x44 1/8, “Cambria” гарнитурда рақамли босма усулида
босилди. Босма табағи: 22,6. Адади: 100 нусха.

Буюртма: № 1278 Нархи шартнома асосида
100190, Тошкент ш., Рихсий кўчаси, 9 уй.

“Lesson press” босмаҳонасида чоп этилди.

Тўплам қуйидаги сайтга жойлаштирилган:

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш Академияси
сайти: www.proacademy.uz